

first to the formation of benzaldehyde and then the oxidation of benzaldehyde to give benzoic acid. It is observed that the amount of benzoic acid starts decreasing slightly after 180 min which can be attributed to its further slow oxidation and polymerisation to give resin⁹.

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Some New Initiators (Simple and Redox) for Polymerization

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THE possibility of initiation with halogen-source materials was visualized during the study of such with halogens^{1,2}. Some new initiator systems (most of them containing halogen or halogen-source material as one component) are depicted herein.

The polymerization was carried out in the dark by wrapping the vessels with black paper. Photopolymerization was done in pyrex sealing tubes with PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ in anhydrous media. Yield by PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ containing systems was always corrected with a blank. $SOCl_2$ was added from micro-pipette and the concentration of PCl_5 was measured by hydrolysis followed by acidimetric titrations. H_2S bubbled through N_2 -flushed water and aqueous I_2 -water were used. H_2S concentration was determined by precipitation with excess $CuSO_4$ solution followed by iodometric titrations.

PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$: From Table 1 it follows that PCl_5 acts as a photoinitiator whereas $SOCl_2$ does not do so. As shown by end group analysis chlorine atoms are produced from PCl_5 or its complex with benzene. In contrast with PCl_5 a good thermal initiating system is formed with $SOCl_2$, evidently due to formation of chlorine radicals by thermal decomposition at as low a temperature as 70° , either in bulk or in solution in a typical solvent viz. petroleum ether. In the latter case the chlorine radicals first formed may attack the hydrocarbon and produce active hydrocarbon radical. There is a basic difference in PCl_5 and $SOCl_2$ systems since in the former case, except under U V., chlorine end group is absent. Moderate values (η) even in high concentration of the initiators are also a distinguishing feature of these systems.

A few other redox initiating systems: H_2S is the simplest thiol member and progress of polymerization using H_2S is hindered probably by high chain terminating action of SH radicals (Table 2). The failure of $KMnO_4$ -HCl system raises a question regarding the involvement of chlorine atoms as an intermediate in this reaction and its role as initiator. The formation of I_2 -redox in both aqueous and non-aqueous medium (Tables 2 and 3) is surprising in view of the normal inhibiting action of I_2 .

TABLE 1—POLYMERIZATION WITH HALOGEN-SOURCE MATERIAL

Halogen source material concentration	Second redox component concn.	Monomer (MMA) concn.	Condition of polymerization (time, temp. etc.)	Polymer yield %	$[\eta]$ in benzene at 30°	Polymer end group
PCl_5 , $2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ (in benzene solution)	x	7.8 M	Wrapped in black paper and kept for 6 hours at 70°	nil	—	—
$SOCl_2$, 0.1 M	X	Bulk, 5 ml	At U.V. (40°) for $2\frac{1}{2}$ hr	10%	1.2	Chlorine
$SOCl_2$, 0.10 M	X	Bulk, 1 ml	At U.V. (40°) for 3 hr	nil	—	—
PCl_5 , 0.12 M (in $CHCl_3$ solution)	Benzyl Alcohol	4.7 M	At 70° for 4 hr	34.3%	1.8	Chlorine
	0.23 M		At 30° 24 hr	8%	0.5	—
PCl_5 , $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ (in benzene solution)	n-butyl amine, 0.34 M	8.9 M	At 70° for 3 hr	5%	0.6	Amine
	Isobutyl alcohol, 0.14 M			<1%	—	—
	Hexadecyl mercaptan, 0.1 M	8.8 M	At 60° , 3 hr	52%	1.1	—
$SOCl_2$, 0.1 M	Solvent Petroleum ether, 2.4% v/v	8.9 M	At 70° , 4 hr	18%	1.5	Chlorine
$SOCl_2$, 0.09 M	Pet. ether 20% v/v	7.5 M	"	16%	0.9	"
$SOCl_2$, 0.035 M	Pet. ether 66% v/v	3.1 M	"	17%	0.2	"

TABLE 2—AQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION

Monomer concentration = 0.094M, Temperature = 30°					
First redox component	Second redox component	Induction period (Approx.)	Time in hr	Polymer yield %	$[\eta]$ in benzene at 30°
H ₂ S, $1.3 \times 10^{-2} M$	Cl ₂ , $1 \times 10^{-5} M$	3 min	24	<1	—
H ₂ S, $2.6 \times 10^{-2} M$	Br ₂ , $2.3 \times 10^{-5} M$	Fraction of a second	24	<1	—
H ₂ S, $0.65 \times 10^{-2} M$	I ₂ , $0.2 \times 10^{-5} M$	10 hr	24	<1	—
K-oxalate, $1.3 \times 10^{-3} M$	I ₂ , $3.2 \times 10^{-5} M$	$\frac{1}{2}$ hr	24*	35	1.5
Isobutyl alcohol $2.2 \times 10^{-2} M$	Cl ₂ , $2.7 \times 10^{-5} M$	12 hr	24	8	1.2
CS ₂ , 0.06% v/v	Cl ₂ , $1.8 \times 10^{-5} M$	10 hr	24	6	0.9
HCl, $6.0 \times 10^{-3} M$	KMnO ₄ , $1.3 \times 10^{-5} M$	—	24	0	—

* under U. V. radiation

TABLE 3—NONAQUEOUS POLYMERIZATION

First redox component concentration	Second redox component concentration	Monomer concentration	Condition of polymerization : time, temp. etc.	Polymer yield %	$[\eta]$ in benzene at 30°
Ethyl mercaptan $1.5 \times 10^{-1} M$	Br ₂ in C ₆ H ₆ , $2.1 \times 10^{-2} M$	MMA, 7.5 M	4½ hr at 60°	25	0.8
n-Dodecyl mercaptan $4 \times 10^{-2} M$	Br ₂ in TBA, $4.1 \times 10^{-2} M$	MMA, 5.6 M	4 hr at 60°	20	1.0
Acetone, 0.34 M	I ₂ in C ₆ H ₆ , $3.7 \times 10^{-3} M$	MMA, 9.2 M	24 hr at 30°, then at 60° for 3 hr	45	1.2
Isobutyl alcohol, 0.26 M	I ₂ in C ₆ H ₆ , $3.7 \times 10^{-3} M$	MMA, 9.2 M	" "	20	1.3
Isobutyl alcohol $5.4 \times 10^{-2} M$	Br ₂ in C ₆ H ₆ , $5.2 \times 10^{-2} M$	MMA, 4.7 M	5½ hr at 60°	11	2.0
*Ce(SO ₄) ₂ , 4H ₂ O in formamide, $1.18 \times 10^{-3} M$	NH ₂ SO ₂ H in formamide $5.2 \times 10^{-3} M$	MMA, 1.9 M	24 hr at 30°	30	1.5
DMF, 3.4 M	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ , $2 \times 10^{-3} M$	MMA**, 7.1 M	72 hr at 30°	8	2.5
DMF, 13.7 M	K ₂ Cr ₂ O ₇ , $2 \times 10^{-3} M$	Acrylamide, 1.4 M	72 hr at 30°	60	3.2

* Done at the instance of Dr. T. K. Chatterjee.

** A phase separation occurs and the polymerization proceeds in the separated phase. Concentrations given are overall concentrations.

In the bi-phasic DMF-K₂Cr₂O₇-MMA system (Table 3), MMA of the DMF layer is constantly utilised by K₂Cr₂O₇-DMF layer and according to expectation a better yield is obtained with the homogeneous DMF-K₂Cr₂O₇ Acrylamide system.

A non-aqueous ceric system is interesting in view of several aqueous Ce⁴⁺ systems⁸.

Thiol-oxygen initiating system : That only a limited amount of oxygen is helpful for polymerization is proved by the following experiment. 2-mercaptoethanol ($4.4 \times 10^{-2} M$), MMA (0.094M), reaction (for 72 hr. at 30°) in systems flushed with oxygen or nitrogen → no polymerization but reaction in ordinary aqueous (i.e. in air) systems → 50% polymerization. Same conclusion is obtained using thiophenol or thiocresol or with the following general polymerization condition : Acrylamide (2.3M), 2-mercaptoethanol ($1.2 \times 10^{-2} M$) in water for 24 hr at 30° and then 4 hr at 50°. Flushing condition and yield : N₂ flushing for 10 min - 0% yield, N₂ flushing for 1 min. - 7.8% yield, unflushed - 90% yield. Evidently all previous work with thiol as redox initiator is suspected unless this point has been taken care of.

A new complex between H₂S and DMF : A thermoreversible complex is formed with H₂S and DMF (yellow at 0° and blue at 30°). Initiation with this complex is under study ; it has been seen to give polymers in combination with Br₂ in DMF medium.

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